

IS CERNA-JIU FAULT (SOUTH CARPATHIANS, ROMANIA) BEING REACTIVATED?

BEHAVIOUR PATTERNS RESEMBLING THOSE ENCOUNTERED AT THE WESTERN TERMINATION OF THE NORTH ANATOLIAN FAULT

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Two basement nappe systems (designated as “Lower Danubian” and “Upper Danubian” respectively) occupy the lowermost structural position within the South Carpathians Alpine nappe pile (Iancu et al., 2005). Each of those two Danubian units includes a Neoproterozoic metamorphic rocks basement, overlain by a Mesozoic (Liassic to Late Cretaceous) sedimentary cover. In the SW extremity of the South Carpathians, a major control on the geometry of the contact between the two Danubian nappe systems has been exerted by the Tertiary age Cerna-Jiu strike-slip major fault, for which a dextral average displacement of 35 km was estimated (Berza and Drăgănescu, 1988).

Along the Cerna-Jiu fault, the South Carpathians orogen has been completing a clockwise rotation around the Moesian Platform western edge. The last stage of this process has been accompanied (e.g., Linzer et al., 1998) by extensional deformation resulting in the opening, during the Badenian (ca. 15 Ma ago), of several sedimentary basins: Bahna, Orșova, Donji Milanovac, Mehadia, Bozovici, Liubcova. Those pull-apart and transtensional basins became disconnected from each other after the Badenian, then sedimentation progressively ceased – last, during the Early Pannonian (ca. 8 Ma ago), in Mehadia basin.

The more recent evolution of the region is less well-constrained. It could only be conjectured (Leever, 2007) that significant differential uplift operated after the Early Pannonian, given that the maximum present-day elevation at which Badenian sediments occur in the Liubcova, Orșova and Donji Milanovac basins is less than 500 m, while in the nearby Mehadia basin it exceeds 700 m. Differential uplift has been invoked also by ter Borgh (2013), as a possible cause for the obvious disequilibrium which nowadays exists between the catchments of the two main rivers of this region - the Danube and the Jiu: the Danube has only short tributaries which, nonetheless, exert stream piracy at the expense of the Jiu drainage area. The entire present-day catchment of Jiu is developed on deposits belonging to the former Dacian Basin, where continental-fluviatile sedimentation was definitely established (Jipa and Olariu, 2009) no earlier than the Dacian to Romanian transition (~4 Ma). Hence the obviously unstable drainage divide between the Danube and the Jiu catchments – and, implicitly, the present-day Danube course, the Iron Gates gorge included – has to be younger. It is worth mentioning, in addition, that the Danube terraces seem to indicate accelerated uplift rates in the Quaternary (the resulting incision being in excess of 100 m - Leever, 2007). It is hence reasonable to assume that some significant tectonic activity has concerned the considered region since ~4 Ma. Present-day seismic activity, together with discharges of thermal water accompanied by

large concentrations of He could be signatures of that tectonic activity that initiated no earlier than ~4 Ma ago.

The seismic hazard posed by the region became conspicuous on the occurrence, on 18 July 1991, of an MS = 5.6 event located at 11.6 km depth (International Seismological Centre, 2019). In about the same epicentral position, on 11 October 1910 there had occurred (Shebalin et al., 1998) another instrumentally recorded earthquake, for which a magnitude (MS) of 4.3 was estimated, the computed depth being rather similar (11 km) to that of the 18 July 1991 event.

There is a remarkable space-proximity between the epicenters of those two earthquakes, and the locations of the well-known thermal groundwater outflows of Băile Herculane. The latter are traditionally inferred to be the result of mixing between various parent-waters (e.g., Povară et al., 2008). In the present study, the mixing regime associated to Băile Herculane thermal outflows (specifically, Venera I and Neptun III springs, Traian and Diana III wells) has been investigated by means of reciprocal concentration plots involving solutes which behaved conservatively. In one such Ca^{2+} vs. Cl^- plot (Fig. 1a), the very tight regression which could be fitted to the data-points confirms that that the considered outflows are derived ensuing to mixing - subject to various mixing ratios - between two distinct parent-waters.

Fig. 1. Reciprocal concentration plots, constructed for: (a) the dissolved cation Ca^{2+} , versus the dissolved anion Cl^- ; (b) He in the associated gas phase, versus the dissolved anion Cl^-

It was yet rather unexpected to notice that the thermal fluid discharged by a borehole located some 20 km away from Băile Herculane, at Mehadica, had chemical characteristics very similar to the low mineralization parent-water inferred to contribute to the Băile Herculane mixtures: specifically, a virtually zero Ca^{2+} content, associated to a non-negligible concentration of Cl^- (amounting to ~500 mg/L – Fig. 1a). Additional support for the conjectured mixing processes that involve the Mehadica borehole fluid, as well as the

considered Băile Herculane discharges, is provided by the associated gas composition. The “Mehadica-type” fluid - which likely progressively dilutes, at Băile Herculane, the strongly mineralized parent-water - contributes also with He to the gas phase associated (Cosma and Ristoiu, 1999) to the Băile Herculane thermal outflows. The fact that an increasing contribution of saline water is accompanied (Fig. 1b) by a progressive reduction of the He percentage in the total released gas, indicates that a geofluid endmember which is He-rich (and which was detected in Mehadica well), progressively mixes, toward Venera spring and Traian well, with another endmember-gas, of a much poorer He content.

The identified large concentrations of He originate mostly in radioactive decay of U and Th existing within the crust. Evidence in this respect is provided (Cosma et al., 2003) by the $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ isotope-ratios: the corresponding values range from 0.075 to 0.117 (expressed as R/Ra - measured/atmospheric ratio), indicating a negligible input of mantle-derived He.

The most likely setting which could explain the outlined mixing patterns should involve a common thermal groundwater (having dissolved Cl^- and Ca^{2+} contents similar to those of Mehadica borehole, as well as large percentages of He in the associated gas phase), which originates somewhere at depth, within the Mehadia basin basement or within its overlying sedimentary formations: part of that common fluid flows toward the Mehadica borehole, while another fraction flows toward the considered outflows at Băile Herculane, where it mixes with another parent-water - more concentrated in Cl^- and Ca^{2+} , and whose associated gas phase is He-deficient. The flowpaths followed by that common fluid must have a WNW-ESE orientation – at odds with the inherited SSW-NNE structural trend that is outlined both by the Cerna-Jiu fault, and by the adjoining nappes boundaries.

Still along the inferred flowpaths, a crustal structure of WNW-ESE orientation has been detected by seismic tomography (Zaharia et al., 2017) as a low P-wave velocity body occurring above ~15 km depth. That lineament possibly corresponds to a highly fractured, fluid-saturated crustal region. The SSW-NNE-directed extensional stress required for opening those fractures is consistent with the normal-faulting indicated by the 18 July 1991 strong ($M_S = 5.6$) earthquake focal mechanism (actually, the only fault plane solution provided by global catalogues for this seismic region).

As suggested by the absence of mantle helium signatures, the fractures involved in the concerned extensional process reach only down to crustal depths. Overall, the considered setting exhibits remarkable similarities with the Sperchios rift, in Central Greece: that actively spreading tectonic structure corresponds, at its turn, to a low P-wave velocity anomaly detected in the 8-12 km depth range (Karastathis et al., 2011), and whose strike is consistent with the extensional deformation indicated by local earthquakes, most of which are of normal fault type (e.g., Ganas et al., 2014), and. Moreover, geofluids discharging in that rift zone include - similarly to those from Mehadica and Băile Herculane – He of almost exclusively crustal provenance (D’Alessandro et al., 2014; Pik and Marty, 2009).

The Sperchios rift activation is inferred to mirror (Armijo et al., 1996) transcurrent deformation in response to the Quaternary propagation of the western tip of the strike-slip North Anatolian Fault. Hence, if a parallel is drawn with the ongoing pull-apart processes involved in the development of the low P-wave velocity lineament detected between Mehadica and Băile Herculane, this would imply that transcurrent deformation might be operating nowadays also along the Cerna-Jiu fault. This is in contrast with the fact that no outcrop-scale signatures of post Miocene activity of the Cerna-Jiu fault have been recognized so far (Krstekanić et al., 2019).

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